

Phytochemical and Pharmacological Investigation of *Heliotropium ellipticum* Ledeb.

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Heliotropium ellipticum Ledeb., Syn. *Heliotropium eichwaldi* Steud. (Fam. : Boraginaceae) is a herb found growing widely in various parts of India. It is employed as an emetic and in snake bite¹ and the extract was found to produce hypotensive effect in mice². A survey of literature reports the isolation of pyrrolizidine alkaloids from its aerial parts³⁻⁶. However, no studies on the non-alkaloidal constituents and roots are reported so far.

The present communication reports the results of phytochemical and biological investigations of some constituents of this plant

Aerial parts : The air-dried and finely powdered aerial parts of *H. ellipticum* (collected from Durgapura farm, near Jaipur) were exhaustively extracted with ethanol (95%) for 8 h thrice. The concentrated ethanolic mass was reextracted with petroleum ether and this fraction after concentration was chromatographed over a column of silica gel. Elution of column with solvents of increasing polarity gave compounds 1-5 which were identified by analytical and spectral (comparative with authentic sample) studies : 1 : octacosane, pet. ether, m.p. 63-64° (EtOAc), ν_{\max} (nujol) 730, 720 cm^{-1} , M^+ 394; 2 : methyl nonadecyl ketone, pet. ether, m.p. 66-67° (EtOAc), ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 710, 720, 715 cm^{-1} , M^+ 310; 295 (M^+ -CH₃), 267 (M^+ -COCH₃); 3 : tricosyl alcohol, pet. ether-C₆H₆ (4 : 1), m.p. 70-72° (EtOAc), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 075, 725, 720 cm^{-1} , M^+ 340; 4 : β -sitosterol, pet. ether-C₆H₆ (3 : 2), m.p. 137° (MeOH), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 665, 1 052 cm^{-1} , M^+ 414; 5 : lanosterol, pet. ether-C₆H₆ (2 : 3), m.p. 139-40° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 630, 1 380, 1 360, 1 110 cm^{-1} , M^+ 426⁷.

Roots : The air-dried and powdered roots of the plant were extracted with ethanol. After removal of waxy components, the residual extract was treated with 5% H₂SO₄ and filtered. Further work-up for the isolation of basic alkaloids^{3,6} afforded compounds 6 and 7 from ether fraction, and 8 from chloroform fraction : 6 : heliotrine, m.p. 123-24° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 550-3 350 br, 1 730, 1 645, 1 380, 1 375, 1 230, 1 160, 1 100 and 1 050 cm^{-1} ; 7 : lasiocarpine, m.p. 94-96° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 480-3 400 br, 1 735, 1 650, 1 180 and 1 110 cm^{-1} ; 8 : europine, m.p. 115° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 550-3 380 br, 1 720, 1 650, 1 170 and 1 100 cm^{-1} ⁶.

The isolation of non-basic alkaloids of the roots was carried out from the defatted methanolic extract⁸ in which

the residue containing *N*-oxides of alkaloids were reduced by Zn-H₂SO₄ to the basic forms. The corresponding basic alkaloids obtained from chloroform fraction were then identified : 9 : indicine-*N*-oxide isolated as indicine, m.p. 97-98° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 500-3 410 br, 1 710, 1 650, 1 150 and 1 090 cm^{-1} ; 10 : lasiocarpine-*N*-oxide isolated as lasiocarpine, m.p. 95-96° (MeOH : Me₂CO), ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 480-3 400 br, 1 735, 1 650, 1 180 and 1 110 cm^{-1} ⁹.

Bioactivity : Ethanolic extract of the aerial parts and roots were screened separately for antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral and antitumor activities against bacteria *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella aerogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, fungi *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium moniliforme* and *Rhizotonia bataticola* by disc-diffusion method⁹ and against virus *Poliomyelitis*, *Measles*, *Herpes simplex*, *Coxsackie*, *Semliki forest* and *Vesicular stomatitis* by plaque inhibition method¹⁰. Antitumor activity was screened using Sarcoma-180 Å (in mice) as the test system¹².

The ethanolic extract of aerial parts and roots inhibited the growth of nearly all the test fungi but the extract of aerial parts was found to be more effective against *R. bataticola* (IZ = 20 mm at 1000 µg/disc; IZ = 13 mm at 500 µg/disc and IZ of mycostatin = 22 mm at 100 units/disc) whereas the extract of root was effective against *A. flavus* (IZ = 14 mm at 1000 µg/disc and IZ of mycostatin = 21.8 mm at 100 units/disc). On the other hand, only the ethanolic extract of roots demonstrated significant degree of tumor inhibitory property (21.3%, GR : ++) which could be attributed to the presence of indicine-*N*-oxide as it is already known to inhibit various tumor systems¹³.

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